

Benefits and Risks of Consuming Edible Insects

Pura Yashung^{a,*}, Karsing Megu^a, Jaya Narah^a, and Jharna Chakravorty^a

^aBiochemical Nutritional Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Rajiv Gandhi University, Doimukh- 791112, Arunachal Pradesh, India.

Abstract: Insect eating has been reported for a long time, and they are consumed in raw and processed forms by several cultures around the world, especially in developing countries, where they are typically regarded as a delicacy in addition to providing nutrients, farming, processing, and consumption of edible insects have recently sparked a lot of research interest, mostly in an effort to mitigate food insecurity and improve nutrition in many developing nations. Edible insects have been demonstrated to improve the nutritional content of foods by providing micro- and macronutrient levels that are comparable to, if not higher than, those found in animal-derived foods. Even with all of these advantages, promoting edible insect cultivation and consumption in developed and developing countries faces a number of hurdles. In many Western countries, however, consumer acceptance of insects as a food source remains a major challenge. The problem of food safety is at the top of the list of these challenges, with many western consumers concerned about the microbiological and chemical health risks that edible insects or edible insect-derived foods may provide. According to the available research, there is a clear need to strike a balance between the nutritional benefits of edible insects and its food safety concerns.

Keywords: Edible insects, Entomophagy, Food safety, Food security

Introduction

Insects found in agricultural, aquatic, and forest ecosystems are an important world biomass resource (New, 2009). The practice of eating insects as an alternative source of food also known as entomophagy (Pager, 1973), has long been a feature of human history (Meyer-Rochow, 2010; Evans, 2015) and prehistory (Backwell & Errico, 2001; Pager, 1976) and are still part of the human diet in many parts of the world. Insect ingestion is thought to be a part of the traditional diets of approximately two billion people around the world (van Huis et al., 2013). People in the United States, South Africa, and Spain have consumed ants, beetle larvae, ticks, termites, lice, and mites since prehistoric times, according to studies (Lesnik, 2014). Although, as compared to traditional meat consumption or the vegetarian movement, entomophagy is not relatively a new concept, it has been present for over a century. Many ethnic groups in Asia, Africa, South America, and Mexico consume edible insects as street food, snacks, or as part of a meal (Zhao, 2007). Eating edible insects dates back over 7000 years (Ramos-Elorduy, 2009). More than 2300 edible insect species from 18 orders have already been reported, with

*Corresponding author: purayashung78@gmail.com

Received on: 12.04.2020, Accepted on: 27.10.2020

Cite as: Yashung, P. et al. 2020. Benefits and Risks of Consuming Edible Insects, Dera Natung Government College Research Journal, 5, 35-48.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.56405/dngcrj.2020.05.01.05>

5 orders having at least 100 records. These insects can be found in both terrestrial and aquatic habitats (Jongema, 2017). Although certain species are farmed on a massive scale, the majority of them are being gathered from nature.

Insects that are commonly consumed includes Coleoptera (beetles) (31 %), Hemiptera (cicadas, planthoppers, leafhoppers, true bugs, and scale insects) (10 %), Hymenoptera (ants, wasps and bees,) (14 percent), Diptera (flies) (2%), Lepidoptera (caterpillars) (18 %), Orthoptera (crickets, grasshoppers, and locusts) (13 %), Odonata (dragonflies) (3%), and Isoptera (termites) (3 %) (Jongema 2017). Furthermore, eating insects are beneficial to one's health and nutrition. These insects have a high nutritional value and can be used as a supplementary component in bread or porridge (Vantomme, 2012). Aside from that, eating insects feed human bodies with proteins, calcium, and vitamins (Rumpold, 2015). For example, studies have discovered that most of these edible insects have a higher protein content than meat or fish (Kouřimská & Adámková, 2016). In addition, Aborigine cultures have traditionally employed edible insects as a medical therapy. In China, for example, insects such as bees are used as nutritional elements in a variety of tonics and healthful dishes. Furthermore, China's State Health ministry and State Food and Drug Administration approved the sale of more than 30 ant-containing health items since 1996 (Shen, Li & Ren 2006).

The nutritional aspect of edible insects

In general, insects have apparent nutritional advantages. Their nutritional profiles are remarkably comparable to that of traditional animal meat (Raubenheimer & Rothman 2013) not only for humans, but also for livestock, they have huge potential as a source of active substances and nutrients . Edible insects are a good source of important nutrients that can help humans achieve their nutritional needs. In the recent decade, published scientific research on their nutritional content has increased, and the evidence suggests that edible insects are a rich source of nutrients and can be used to combat malnutrition, with some insect species contributing significantly to the Recommended Dietary Allowance (RDA) (Weru et al., 2021). They are found to be a high-protein, high-fat, high-vitamin, mineral, and high-fiber source of food and their nutritional profile varies greatly depending on the species metamorphic stage, diet, habitat, and environmental circumstances can all affect the nutritional value of insects, even within the same species (Lange, & Nakamura, 2021).

The nutritional profiles of a range of edible insect species have recently improved, and the frequency of entomophagy-related publications published annually has climbed from <10 pre-2012 to 114 in 2020. The general agreement is that edible insects have a good nutritional content and could be a viable substitute to meat and fish in the diet (Rumpold, and Schluter, 2013; van Huis et al., 2013; Hlongwane et al., 2020). However, it is commonly acknowledged that edible insect nutritional profiles differ significantly between species. Within

Coleoptera, for example, Rumpold and Schluter (Rumpold and Schlüter, et al., 2013) discovered a protein content ranging from 8.85–71.1 % on a dry matter basis. Similarly, *R. phoenicis*, *M. bellicosus* and *Z. variegatus*, have been found to exhibit significant variances in protein, lipid, and ash, a mineral content indicator (Omotoso and Adedire, 2007), and also amino acid profiles (Womeni et al., 2009; Awobusuyi, 2021). The amino acid needs for adults given by the World Health Organization are shown alongside the essential and non-essential amino acid composition of widely eaten insect species (WHO, 2007). However, methionine, cysteine, and tryptophan are all missing or present in extremely little amounts in some insects. If these insects make up the majority of a meal, the diet must be balanced. Insects, with the exception of these species, generally satisfy the WHO's amino acid recommendations. By ingesting a reasonable variety of items, the majority of them can offer enough amounts of essential amino acids. On a dry weight basis, the fat content of insects in embryonic stages ranges from 8 to 70%. Various sources of meat, along with all groups of insects, have identical fatty acid contents (Bukkens, 1997). Lepidopteran and Heteropteran larvae have a higher fat content than other edible insects. When compared to other stages of insects, larvae seem to be the best source of fatty acids. Adults are generally slender, with a fat level of less than 20%. Triacylglycerol is the most common type of fat found in insects (Arrese & Soulages 2010). More than 80% of all fats are made up of monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs) and saturated fatty acids (SFAs). Palmitic acid and stearic acid make up the majority of SFAs in insects at various times. Moreover, insects are also rich in vitamins and minerals, yet feeding has been shown to alter their contents in some studies. Biochemical substances like vitamins A, B1–12, C, D, E, and K, that are required for normal growth and health (Kouimská & Adámková 2016), could be provided by them. Caterpillars, for example, are particularly high in B1, B2, and B6 (Rumpold & Schluter 2013). Vitamins A and D are abundant in bee brood (pupae) (Finke 2005). *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*, the red palm weevil, is a rich source of vitamin E. (Bukkens & Paoletti 2005). Edible insects include a wide range of micronutrients, including iron, manganese, magnesium, potassium phosphorus, selenium, sodium, and zinc (Rumpold & Schluter 2013).

Many insects have chitin in their exoskeletons, which supplies a large amount of fibre. Chitin content varies by insect species as well as developmental stage (Finke, 2009), accounting for about 10% of dried weight (van Huis, 2013; Belluco et al., 2013). Purified chitin contains about 90% dietary fibre (Maezaki et al., 1993), which is easily digestible by humans (Paoletti et al., 2007). Chitin and its deacylated derivative, chitosan, may help with cardiovascular and gastrointestinal health, innate and adaptive immunological responses, cholesterol lowering, and wound healing (Tripathi and Singh, 2008; Lee et al., 2008; Prosky, 2000). Further, edible insects are also found to be a great source of calories, with caloric contributions ranging from 290 to over 750 kcal/100 g. (Ramos-Elorduy et al. 1997).

Food security

Food insecurity is likely to rise even more globally, continuing a trend that began in 2014, especially throughout the Caribbean and Latin America, and adding to already high levels in Africa and South Asia (FAO 2020). Moreover by 2050, the world's population is expected to increase by a quarter (UN, 2021), In many regions of the world, per capita meat demand is increasing in tandem with population growth. This is especially noticeable in high-growth regions rather than low-income ones, with the link between prosperity and meat intake is well-documented (Asian, 2012). In low-income countries, the combination of expanding populations and wealth is exacerbating food insecurity challenges (Msangi and Rosegrant, 2012); discovering alternative, much better sustainable protein sources is critical for combating rising under-nutrition and establishing long-term food security (Anankware, et al., 2021).

Entomophagy, or the human consumption of insects, has significant potential in combating these concerns and is extensively practised around the world, particularly among traditional groups (Dickie, 2019). Despite popular belief, communities practising entomophagy see insects as a delicacy instead of a "hardship" food in times of famine (Halloran and Vantomme, 2013); locusts, for example, are regarded to have been popular among the ancient Near East's social elite (Lanfranchi, 2015). With insect species being detected in human coprolites and several researchers even claiming a similarity between insectivory in human and nonhuman primates, it is becoming increasingly obvious that entomophagy had played a vital role in delivering sustenance throughout hominin evolution (Tommaseo-Ponzetta, 2005). There is a large diversity of edible insect species (Anankware et al., 2015; van Huis et al., 2003), with over 2,000 formally listed species (Jongema, 2017). The popularity of entomophagy, as well as the species consumed, varies greatly around the globe. Edible insect farming, consumption and processing, have recently sparked a lot of research interest, mostly in an effort to alleviate food insecurity and improve nutrition in many developing nations. Edible insects have been demonstrated to improve the nutritional content of foods by providing micro- and macronutrient levels that are comparable to, if not higher than, those found in animal-derived foods. They can be utilised to directly target the first three Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations in this way (zero hunger, no poverty, well-being and good health). Edible insect production also aids in the mitigation of climate change's negative consequences and the improvement of biodiversity, both of which contribute to food security (Imathiu, 2019).

Risks related to consumption of edible insects

Problems can arise even while consuming edible insect species and handling them. Consumption of insects during unsuitable stages of development, improper culinary preparation, handling without safety equipment, or gathering of insects from unsuitable places can all cause negative reactions.

Allergies

A food allergy (Johansson et al., 2004) is an immunological reaction to food that is triggered by compounds known as allergens. Food allergies can cause significant sickness and even death. Food allergy is a significant public health concern whose care along the food value chain remains a serious challenge for the food industry and medical professionals across the world. Sensitive people might be allergic to a wide range of foods, and any protein-containing food can potentially produce an allergic reaction in sensitive people (Boye et al., 2012).

Proteins are the most abundant component of edible insects. Some insects and insect-derived foods may be viable allergen sources. Some types of edible insect proteins such as arginine kinase are considered allergens, according to Murefu and colleague (Murefu et al., 2019). Because insects are linked to crustaceans, the possibility of them causing food allergies has been hypothesized. According to a study conducted in Belgium, skin prick tests produced using grilled *A. domesticus* and *T. molitor* insect samples sensitised 19 % of people, implying that a broad population could be at risk of having allergic reactions if certain edible insects species are consumed (Francis et al., 2019). Likewise, Okezie and colleagues (2010) documented the case of a 36-year-old woman who experienced two bouts of anaphylactic shock after eating mopane caterpillars (The patient had eaten this mopane worm before and had no adverse responses). There was no skin prick test in this case.

Pener reviewed food allergy to insects, including grasshoppers and locusts, in 2014, and found seven cases of severe allergic reactions after eating fried crickets and grasshoppers during a two year duration in a Thai hospital emergency room. In addition, between 1980 and 2007, the Chinese literature reported 27 cases of anaphylactic shock induced by grasshopper intake and 27 cases caused by locust consumption (Pener, 2014). The majority of people who eat edible insects have a little to no chance of developing allergic reactions, specifically if they have never had an allergy before. However, because frequent exposure to an allergen might cause sensitivity, insects should be consumed with caution when first introduced into the diet. To assess the hazards of edible insect dietary allergy, more research is needed.

Pathogenic microorganisms in edible insects

Recent research on the microbial potential hazards associated with edible insects has revealed the potential existence of harmful bacteria in these diets (Garofalo et al., 2017). Many potentially human harmful bacterial taxa, such as *Vibrio*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Clostridium*, and *Bacillus*, were found in a study assessing the variety of microbiota found in edible insects prepared and sold in Thailand (Osimani et al., 2017).

Parasites in insects

The prevalence of parasites in insects is widely documented in a study of food borne pathogenic intestinal flukes in Southeast Asia, which detailed the isolation of 6 distinct species from insects; there is a long, widespread tradition of insect ingestion in this region. Food - borne illnesses caused by transmission of parasites

(trematodes) belonging to the families Lecithodendridae and Plagiorchiidae has been hypothesised based on evidence from human autopsy and insect analyses (Chai et al., 2009). Another parasitic zoonotic agent that could infect people through insect eating is *Dicrocoelium dendriticum*. The infection is caused by eating ants that carry metacercariae, however pseudo-infections (the presence of *D. dendriticum* eggs in the faeces but no adult worms) are caused by eating infected animal liver. In the urban area of Kyrgyzstan, the frequency in children (2 to 15 years old) was 8.0 %, despite the diagnostic test failing to separate between infection and pseudo-infection (Jeandron et al., 2011).

The scientific literature contains only rare evidence of potentially hazardous parasites in edible insects. A well-managed closed farm setting, on the other hand, would be clean and free of all the hosts required for parasite life cycles to be completed. In every case, adequate management before eating, relying on freezing, boiling and cooking, could limit dangers, especially with picked rather than farmed insects (Belluco et al., 2015).

Fungi

Insects may also carry fungus and yeasts that can be harmful to both animals and humans. Fresh, freeze-dried, and frozen insects (*L. migratoria* and *T. molitor*) all included significant levels of yeasts and fungi (FASFC, 2014). A study from Botswana emphasised the significance of adequate handling, processing, drying, and storage when unacceptable concentrations of aflatoxins were discovered in some commercial batches of mopane worms (*Gonimbrasia belina*: Saturniidae) (Schabel, 2010). Some fungi (*Aspergillus* sp., *Penicillium* sp.) were isolated from the same species and dried under laboratory conditions, among which are also mycotoxigenic species (Simpunya et al., 2000). Fungi related with insects produced for feed and food, or introduced during processing, storage, and farming, could provide a concern in general.

Heavy metal contamination in edible insects

For five distinct varieties of edible arthropods, cadmium and lead concentrations varied from 0.02–0.07 mg/kg and 0.03–0.10 mg/kg dry weight, respectively (Banjo et al., 2010). Dried grasshoppers also known as Chapulines were suspected of causing high blood lead levels in residents of a California neighbourhood (Handley et al., 2007). The latter researchers looked at the causes of a lead poisoning outbreak in Monterey County, California. Between 2001 and 2003, they wanted to look into risk factors for high blood lead concentrations (> 10 g/dL) in pregnant women and children in three county health department clinics. One cause of lead poisoning was thought to be homemade dried grasshoppers (chapulines) being sent Oaxaca, Mexico. Significant quantities of lead were found in these chapulines from the total of ten chapuline samples collected in Zimatlan, Oaxaca, there was a wide range of lead content, ranging from undetectable to 2500 mg/kg (Handley et al., 2007).

Blue bottle (*Calliphora vomitoria*), House fly (*M. domestica*), black soldier fly (*H. illucens*), and blow fly (*Chrysomya* sp.) cultivated using a wide range of substrates and methods of production at various geographic locations were evaluated for metals in an investigation of the chemical safety of farmed insects (Charlton et al., 2015). Cadmium was found at amounts in some edible insect samples that exceeded the highest residual limit for entire animal feed, but this was not the issue for the other metals tested. In a field research using phytophagous larvae of the Noctuid moth (*Spodoptera litura*), no cadmium or lead bioaccumulation was identified, despite significant quantities of these metals in larval faeces (Zhuang et al., 2009). Because metal buildup in insects is influenced by a variety of parameters such as age, physiology, sex, and heredity. In addition, according to Idowu and colleague in 2014, some termite species have a lesser tendency to accumulate heavy metals (Idowu et al. 2014). Further, Banjo in 2010 detected significant amounts of nickel, cadmium, lead, zinc, and sodium in the larvae of *Anapleptes trifasciata* (beetle) and *Rhynchophorus phoenicis* (beetle). Diener and his colleague in 2015 found that cadmium accumulation ranged between 2.32 and 2.94%, lead stayed below its baseline concentration in feed, and zinc reduced from 0.97 to 0.39%. When the black soldier fly *H. illucens* was fed chicken feed contaminated with cadmium, lead, and zinc, the black soldier fly *H. illucens* level of cadmium, lead, and zinc was spiked (Diener et al. 2015). Finally, the major route of contamination for edible insects appears to be heavy metal transfer from substrates (e.g. plants, organic matter). The amount of metal accumulated is determined on the insect species, growth stage, and the metal in question.

Antinutrients

Antinutrients, also known as antinutritional factors, are generally occurring compounds in meals that hinder the intake, absorption, digestion, and use of nutrients (including macro- and micronutrients) (Akande et al., 2004). These chemicals, which are more frequent and have larger concentrations in plant-based foods than that in animal-based foods, may have other negative health impacts on consumers depending on the kind and concentration in foods. Antinutrients of various sorts have been identified and quantified in a number of edible insect species. Antinutrients (hydrocyanide, tannin, oxalate, and phytate) were discovered and measured in four species of insects in Nigeria (Ekop et al. 2010). Long-horned beetles, grasshoppers, meal bugs, and termites are among the insect species shown to contain phytates and tannins (Musundire et al., 2016). Saponins and alkaloids are two more antinutrients that have been found and studied in edible insects (Musundire et al., 2014). In order to create strategies of either eliminating antinutrients before consumption, avoiding eating of the implicated insect kinds, or seeking an alternate insect type for consumption, it is necessary to know what antinutrients are found in particular insect species.

Conclusion

Due to global growing population, rising demand for and cost of animal protein, food shortages in some parts of the world, and increasing environmental challenges, the utilisation of edible insects as a source of food for humans has been a topic of global concern. One of the most pressing global concerns is ensuring environmentally sustainable food security. The research suggests edible insects can potentially play a key role in resolving food and nutrition insecurity, and this should be emphasized. Scientific evidence reveals that the nutritional quality of edible insects is comparable to, and sometimes even exceeds, that of animal-based diets. This, along with the fact that edible insects grow quicker, convert more food, and require fewer resources to nurture than cattle, should make them an even more appealing quality food source, particularly for the rural poor in developing countries. Edible insects might generally be recognised as safe (GRAS) foods in nations or communities where entomophagy is practised, but that is not the situation in most developed nations, where most consumers are cautious of their safety and consequently hesitant to incorporate them in their diets. There is a scarcity of scientific information on edible insect food safety issues. More research is needed to better understand the dangers associated with their intake in order to protect consumer health. As a result, entomophagy should be promoted and supported worldwide, but there must be a balance maintained between consumer worries about food safety as well as the nutritional and health advantages of this food type. The development and implementation of edible insect legislation rules in both emerging and developed nations should be promoted, as this can help facilitate commerce in this commodity in the long run, in addition to assuring safety. Future research towards up-scaling edible insect production and marketing should be prioritised.

References

- Adeduntan, S.A. 2005.** Nutritional and antinutritional characteristics of some insects foraging in Akura forest reserve Ondo state, Nigeria. *J. Food Technol.*, 3, 563-567.
- Akande, K.E., Doma, U.D., Agu, H. and Adamu, H.M. 2010.** Major antinutrients found in plant protein sources: their effect on nutrition. *Pak. J. Nutr.*, 9, 827-832.
- Anankware JP, Fening KO, Osekre E, Obeng-Ofori D. 2015.** Insects as food and feed. *Int. J. Agric. Res.* 3:143–151.doi: 10.1002/fsat.3201_7.
- Anankware, J.P., Robert, B.J., Cheseto, X., Osuga, I., Savolainen, V., and Collins, C.M. 2021.** The Nutritional Profiles of five Important Edible Insect Species From West Africa-Analytical and Literature Synthesis. *Front. Nutr.*, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.792941>.
- Arrese, E. L., and Soulages, J. L. 2010.** Insect fat body: Energy, metabolism, and regulation. *Annual Review of Entomology.* <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurevento-112408-085356>.

- Asian DB. 2012.** Food Security Poverty in Asia the Pacific: Key Challenges Policy Issues. Available online at: <http://hdl.handle.net/11540/904>.
- Awobusuyi T.D., Siwela M., Pillay K. 2021.** Nutritional composition of insect types most commonly consumed by the Olugboja Community of Ondo State, Nigeria. *Int J Trop Insect Sci.* 41:2975–82.doi: 10.1007/s42690-021-00483-x.
- Banjo A.D., Lawal, O.A., Fasunwon, B.T., Alimi, G.O. 2010.** Alkali and Heavy Metal Contaminants of Some Selected Edible Arthropods in South Western Nigeria. *American-Eurasian, Journal of Toxicological Science,* 2 (1), 25-29.
- Belluco, S., Losasso, C., Maggioletti, M., Cristiana, C. A., Maurizio G. P., and Paoletti, A. R. 2013.** Edible insects in a food safety and nutritional perspective: a critical review *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 12, 296-313.
- Belluco, S., Losasso, C., Maggioletti, M., Alonzi, C., Ricci, A., and Paoletti, M.G. 2015.** Edible insects: a food security solution or a food safety concern? *Animal Frontiers,* 5(2).
- Boye, J., Danquah, A.O., Thang, C., Zhao, X. 2012.** Food allergens. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol.* 3, 798-819.
- Bukkens S.G. 1997.** The nutritional value of edible insects. *Ecol. Food Nutr.* 36, 287-319, 10.1080/03670244.1997.9991521.
- Bukkens, S. G., and Paoletti, M. G. 2005.** Insects in the human diet: nutritional aspects. *Ecological implications of minilivestock; role of rodents, frogs, snails, and insects for sustainable development,* 545–577.
- Chai, J.Y., E.H. Shin, S.H. Lee, and H.J. Rim. 2009.** Foodborne intestinal flukes in Southeast Asia. *Korean J. Parasitol.* 47 (Suppl.): S69–S102.
- Charlton, A.J.; Dickinson, M.; Wakefield, M.E.; Fitches, E.; Kenis, M.; Han, R.; Zhu, F.; Kone, N.; Grant, M.; Devic, E.; Bruggeman, G.; Prior, R.; Smith, R. 2015.** Exploring the chemical safety of fly larvae as a source of protein for animal feed. *Journal of Insects as Food and Feed,* 1(1), 7–16.doi:10.3920/JIFF2014.0020hua
- Dickie F, Miyamoto M, Collins CMT. 2019.** The potential of insect farming to increase food security. In: *Edible Insects,* p. 1–10. doi: 10.5772/intechopen.88106.
- Diener, S., Zurbrugg, C., and Tockner, K. 2015.** Bioaccumulation of heavy metals in the black soldier fly. *Hermetia j. Insects Food and Feed,* 1, 261-270.
- Ekop, E.A., Udoh, A.I., and Akpan, P.E. 2010.** Proximate and anti-nutrient composition of four edible insects in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *World J. Appl. Sci. Technol.,* 2, 224-231.
- FAO IFAD UNICEF WFP WHO. 2020.** The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World. Transforming Food Systems for Affordable Healthy Diets. Rome: FAO.

- FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations), 2013.** Edible insects. Future prospects for food and feed security. van Huis A, van Itterbeeck J, Klunder H, Mertens E, Halloran A, Muir G and Vantomme P. Rome. Available at: <http://www.fao.org/docrep/018/i3253e/i3253e00.htm>
- FASFC (Belgian Scientific Committee of the Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain), 2014.** Food safety aspects of insects intended for human consumption. Common advice of the Belgian Scientific Committee of the Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain (FASFC) and of the Superior Health Council (SHC). Available at: http://www.favv-afsca.fgov.be/scientificcommittee/advice/_documents/ADVISE14_2014_ENG_DOSSIER2014-04.pdf
- Finke, M. D. 2005.** Nutrient composition of bee brood and its potential as human food. *Ecology of Food and Nutrition*, 44(4), 257–270.
- Finke, M.D. 2007.** Estimate of chitin in raw whole insects. *Zoo Biol.*, 26, 105-115.
- Francis, F., Doyen, V., Debaugnies, F., Mazzucchellie, G., Caparrosa, R., Alabia, T., Blecker, E., Haubruge, E., and Corazza, F. 2019.** Limited cross reactivity among arginine kinase allergens from mealworm and cricket edible insects. *Food Chem.*, 276, 714-718.
- Garofalo, C., Osimani A., Milanovic, V., Taccari, M., Cardinali, F., and Aquilanti L. 2017.** The microbiota of marketed processed edible insects as revealed by high-throughput sequencing. *Food Microbiol.* 62, 15-22.
- Halloran A, Vantomme P. 2013.** The Contribution of Insects to Food Security, Livelihoods the Environment. Available online at: www.fao.org/forestry/edibleinsects/en/.
- Handley, M.A. 2007.** Globalization, binational communities, and imported food risks: results of an outbreak investigation of lead poisoning in Monterey County, California. *American Journal of Public Health*, 97(5): 900–906.
- Hlongwane ZT, Slotow R, Munyai TC. 2020.** Nutritional composition of edible insects consumed in Africa: a systematic review. *Nutrients*. 12:1–28.doi: 10.3390/nu12092786
- Idowu, A.B.; Ademolu, K.O.; Bamidele, J.A. 2014.** Nutrition and Heavy Metal Levels in the Mound Termite, *Macrotermes bellicosus* (Smeathman) (Isoptera: Termitidae), at three Sites under Varying Land use in Abeokuta, Southwestern Nigeria. *African Entomology*, 22(1), 156–162.doi:10.4001/003.022.0119
- Imathiu, Samuel (2019).** Benefits and food safety concerns associated with consumption of edible insects. *NFS Journal*, 18, 1-11, S235236461930046X-. doi:10.1016/j.nfs.2019.11.002.
- Evans, J., Alemu, M. H., Flore, R., Frost, M. B., Halloran, A., Jensen, A. B., Maciel-Vergara, G., Meyer-Rochow, V. B., Münke-Svendsen, C., Olsen, S. B., Payne, C., Roos, N., Rozin, P., Tan, H. S. G., van Huis, A., Vantomme, P., & Eilenberg, J. 2015.** 'Entomophagy': an evolving terminology in need of a review. *Journal of Insects as Food and Feed*, 1(4), 293-305. <https://doi.org/10.3920/JIFF2015.0074>

- Jeandron, A., L. Rinaldi, G. Abdylidaeva, J. Usubalieva, P. Steinmann, G. Cringoli, and J. Utzinger. 2011.** Human infections with *Dicrocoelium dendriticum* in Kyrgyzstan: The tip of the iceberg? *J. Parasitol.* 97:1170–1172.
- Ji K, Chen J, Li M, Liu Z, Wang C, Zhan Z, Wu X and Xia Q, 2009.** Anaphylactic shock and lethal anaphylaxis caused by food consumption in China. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 20, 227–231.
- Johanson, S.G., Bieber, T., Dahl, R., Friedmann, P.S., Lanier, B.Q., Lockey, R.F. 2004.** Lockey Revised nomenclature for allergy for global use: report of the Nomenclature Review Committee of the World Allergy Organization, October. *J. Allergy Clin Immunol.* 3, 798-819.
- Jongema Y. 2017.** List of Edible Insects of the World-WUR. Available online at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/Research-Results/Chair-groups/Plant-Sciences/Laboratory-of-Entomology/Edible-insects/Worldwide-species-list.htm>.
- Kouřimská, L., and Adámková, A. 2016.** Nutritional and sensory quality of edible insects. *NFS Journal*, 4, 22-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nfs.2016.07.001>
- Backwell, L.R., d'Errico, F. 2001.** Evidence of termite foraging by Swartkrans early hominids. *Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 98, 1358-1363, [10.1073/pnas.98.4.1358](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.98.4.1358)
- Lanfranchi GB. 2005.** Minilivestock consumption in the ancient near East: the case of locusts. In: *Ecological Implications of Minilivestock: Potential of Insects, Rodents, Frogs and Snails*. Enfield: Science Publisher Inc. p. 163–74.
- Lange K.W., Nakamura Y. 2021.** Edible insects as a source of food bioactive and their potential health effects. *Food Bioact.* 14, 4-9, [10.31665/JFB.2021.14264](https://doi.org/10.31665/JFB.2021.14264)
- Lee, C.G., Da Silva C.A., Lee, J.Y., Harti, D. and Elias, J.A. 2008.** Chitin regulation of immune responses: an old molecule with new roles. *Curr. Opin. Immunol.* 20, 684-689.
- Lesnik, J. J., 2014.** In the hominin diet: A meta-analysis of termite genera, species and castes as a dietary supplement for South African robust australopithecines. *Journal of Human Evolution*, 71, 94- 104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2013.07.015>
- Maezaki, Y., Yamazaki, A., Mizuochi, K. and Tsuji, K. 1993.** Measurement of Dietary Fiber in Chitin and Chitosan by the Enzymatic-Gravimetric Metho. *Journal of the Agricultural Chemical Society of Japan*, 67, 677-684. <https://doi.org/10.1271/nogeikagaku1924.67.677>
- Meyer-Rochow, V.B. 2010.** Entomophagy and its impact on world cultures: the need for a multidisciplinary approach. *Forest Insects as food: humans bite back*, pp.23-36
- Msangi S, Rosegrant MW. 2020.** Feeding the Future's Changing Diets: Implications for Agriculture Markets, Nutrition, and Policy. New Delhi: International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), pp- 8.

- Murefu, T.R., Macheka, L., Musundire, R., Manditsera, F.A. 2019.** Safety of wild harvest and reared edible insects: a review. *Food Control*. 101, 209-224.
- Musundire, R., Osuga, I.M., Cheseto, X., Irungu, J., and Torto, B. 2016.** Aflatoxin contamination detected in nutrient and anti-oxidant rich edible stink bug stored in recycled gain containers. *PLoS One*, 11, 1-16.
- Musundire, R., Zvidzai, C.J., Chidewe, Samende, B.K., and Manditsera, F.A. 2014.** Nutrient and anti-nutrient composition of *Henicus whellani* (Orthoptera: Stenopelmatidae), an edible ground cricket, in south-eastern Zimbabwe. *Int. J. Trop. Insect Sci.*, 34, 223-231.
- New, T.R. 2009.** Insect species conservation by ecology, biodiversity and conservation series, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Nishimune, T., Watanabe, Y., Okazaki, H., and Akai, H. 2000.** Thiamine is decomposed due to *Anophe* spp. Entomophagy in seasonal ataxia patients in Nigeria. *J. Nutr.*, 130, 1625-1628.
- Omotoso OT, Adedire CO. 2007.** Nutrient composition, mineral content and the solubility of the proteins of palm weevil, *Rhynchophorus phoenicis* F. (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *J Zhejiang Univ Sci B.*, 8:318–22.doi: 10.1631/jzus.2007.B0318.
- Osimani, A., Garofalo, C., Milanovic, V., Taccari, M., Cardinali, F., and Aquilanti, L. 2017.** Insight into the proximate composition and microbial diversity of edible insects marketed in the European Union *Eur. Food Res. Technol.*, 243, 1157-1171.
- Okezie, O. A., Kgomotso, K. K., & Letswiti, M. M. 2010.** Mopane worm allergy in a 36-year-old woman: a case report. *Journal of medical case reports*, 4, 42. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1752-1947-4-42>
- Pager, H. 1973.** Rocking painting in southern Africa showing bees and honey hunting *Bee World*, 54, 61-68.
- Pager, H. 1976.** Cave paintings suggest honey hunting activities in ice age times *Bee World*. 57, 9-14.
- Panzani RC and Ariano R, 2001.** Arthropods and invertebrates allergy (with the exclusion of mites): the concept of panallergy. *Allergy*, 56, 1–22
- Paoletti, M.G., Norberto, L., Damini R., and Musumeci S. 2007.** Human gastric juice contains chitinase that can degrade chitin. *Ann. Nutr. Me tab.*, 51, 244-251.
- Pener, M.P. 2014.** Allergy to Locusts and Acridid Grasshoppers: a Review. *Journal of Orthoptera Research*, 23(1), 59–67. doi:10.1665/034.023.0105
- Prosky, L. 2000.** When dietary fiber is considered a functional food? *Biofactors*, 12, 289-297.
- Rumpold BA, Schlüter OK. 2013.** Nutritional composition and safety aspects of edible insects. *Mol Nutr Food Res.* 57:802–23. doi: 10.1002/mnfr.201200735
- Ramos-Elorduy, J. 2009.** Anthro-entomophagy: Cultures, evolution and sustainability. *Entomological Research*, 39(5), 271–288.

- Ramos-Elorduy, J., Moreno, J. M. P., Prado, E. E., Perez, M. A., Otero, J. L., & De Guevara, O. L. 1997.** Nutritional value of edible insects from the state of Oaxaca, Mexico. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 10(2), 142–157
- Raubenheimer, D., and Rothman, J. M. 2013.** Nutritional ecology of entomophagy in humans and other primates. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 58, 141–160. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-120710-100713>
- Rumpold, B. A., and Schluter, O. K. 2013.** Nutritional composition and safety aspects of edible insects. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 57(5), 802–823. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.201200735>.
- Rumpold, B. A., & Schlüter, O. 2015.** Insect based protein sources and their potential for human consumption: Nutritional composition and processing. *Animal Frontiers*, 5(2), 20-24. <https://doi.org/10.2527/af.2015-0015>
- Schabel, H.G. 2010.** Forest Insects as Food: A Global Review. *Proceedings of a Workshop on Asia-Pacific Resources and Their Potential for Development*, Bangkok, 37-64.
- Schroeckenstein D.C., Meier-Davis S. and Bush R.K., 1990.** Occupational sensitivity to *Tenebrio molitor* Linnaeus (yellow mealworm). *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 86, 182–188.
- Schroeckenstein DC, Meier-Davis S, Graziano FM, Falomo A and Bush RK, 1998.** Occupational sensitivity to *Alphitobius diaperinus* (Panzer) (lesser mealworm). *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, 82, 1081–1088.
- Shen, L., Li, D., Feng, F. and Ren, Y. 2006.** Nutritional composition of *Polyrhachis vicina* Roger (edible Chinese black ant). *Songklanakarin Journal of Science and Technology*, 28(1): 107–114.
- Simpanya, M.F. 2000.** Dermatophytes: Their taxonomy, ecology and pathogenicity. *Rev. Iberam. Micol.* 12: 1-12.
- Siracusa A, Marcucci F, Spinozzi F, Marabini A, Pettinari L, Pace ML and Tacconi C, 2003.** Prevalence of occupational allergy due to live fish bait. *Clinical and Experimental Allergy*, 33, 507–510.
- Tommaseo-Ponzetta M. 2005.** Insects: food for human evolution. In: *Ecological Implications of Minilivestock: Potential of Insects, Rodents, Frogs and Snails*. Enfield: Science Publisher Inc., 141–61.
- Tripathi, K., and Singh, A. 2018.** Chitin, chitosan and their pharmacological activities: a review. *J. Pharm. Sci. Res.*, 9, 2626-2635.
- UN. 2019.** World Population Prospects: Ten Key Findings. Available online at: <https://population.un.org/wpp> (accessed June 17, 2021).
- Van Huis, A., van Itterbeeck, J., Klunder, H., Mertens E., Halloran, A., Muir, P., and Vantomme P. 2013.** Edible Insects: Future Prospects for food and feed Security. *FAO Forestry Paper*. Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nation, 1-187.

- Van Huis A. 2003.** Insects as food in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Insect Sci its Appl.* 23:163–85.doi: 10.1017/S1742758400023572.
- Vantomme, P., Mertens, E., Van Huis, A., and Klunder, H. 2012.** Assessing the potential of insects as food and feed in assuring food security. In Summary report, Technical consultation meeting (pp. 23-25).
- Weru, Johnson & Chege, Peter & Kinyuru, John. 2021.** Nutritional potential of edible insects: a systematic review of published data. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science.* 41. 1-23. 10.1007/s42690-021-00464-0.
- WHO, 2007.** Protein and amino acid requirements in human nutrition: report of a joint /WHO/UNU expert consultation, WHO technical report series.
- Womeni HM, Linder M, Tiencheu B, Mbiapo FT, Villeneuve P, Fanni J. 2009.** Oils of insects and larvae consumed in Africa: potential sources of polyunsaturated fatty acids. *OCL Ol Corps Gras Lipides.* 16:230–5.doi: 10.1051/ocl.2009.0279.
- Jongema, Y. 2017.** List of edible insects of the world. <https://www.wur.nl/en/Research-Results/Chairgroups/Plants-Science/Laboratory-of-Entomology/Edible-insects/Worldwide-species-list.htm>
- Zhao, M., He, Z., Sun, L., Wang, C.Y and Ding W.F. 2017.** Edible insects in china: Utilization and prospects. *Insect Science*, 25(2), 1-15.
- Zhuang, P., Zou, H.L., Shu, W.S. 2009.** Biotransfer of heavy metals along a soil– plant–insect–chicken food chain: field study. *J. Environ. Sci.* 21, 849–853.